

THE RELATION BETWEEN SATISFACTION AMONG SPORTS CLUBS' CUSTOMERS AND COACHES' PERSONALITY AND WORK ETHICS

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Abstract:

In terms of manner of data collection, the present research is considered as a descriptive-correlative study and also in terms of purpose, it is considered as an applied research which is carried out under field methods. The population of this research includes the staff and customers of governmental and private pools of the province of Kurdistan. The number of the staff is equal to 135 individuals and according to the Morgan's chart, the sample number was determined as 100 individuals. Since this research includes two separate populations, and only the number of the staff of pools is known; the method of synchronization is employed and the same amount of samples is considered for customers as well. For the purpose of data collection, Gregory C. Petty's (1990) questionnaire of ethics including 23 questions and the factors of interest in work, perseverance, human relations at work environment and collaboration in work was used. The validity of this questionnaire is approved by 15 sports management professors and also its reliability was calculated as 0.81 by the Cronbach's Alpha method. For evaluation of customer satisfaction, the Huang's questionnaire including 19 questions and the components of visuals and looks of the club, personnel, facilities and current equipment. Its validity and reliability are respectively calculated as 0.78 and 0.86. In addition, the short form of questionnaire of personality characteristics was used: aimed at evaluation of players'

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personality characteristics, the short for of the NEO questionnaire including 60 questions was used. This questionnaire was developed by Caste and McCree in 1982. The first translation of this questionnaire into Persian language was prepared by Kiamehr (2005). This test evaluates 5 major personality characteristics which include Neuroticism (N), extraversion (E), openness of mind towards experiences (O), Agreeableness (A), and conscientiousness (C). The Cronbach's alpha method has calculated reliability of different aspects of this questionnaire in the range of 0.63 to 0.84.

Keywords: sports clubs' customers, coaches' personality, work ethics

1. Introduction

Nowadays, ethics is considered as a primary issue and during the recent few years, researchers and theorists have increasingly paid attention to different harmful and negative behaviors in work environments (Gol Parvar, 2012). Modern managers have comprehended that organizations are not supposed to be merely managed by rules and regulations; in fact in addition to these, another tool is required which is known as ethics. In experts' views, for a better management of organizations it is necessary to consider for ethics alongside with rules. In addition, self-control must be replaced with being controlled and also moral purposes must be transformed to moral rules (Coinjock and Jones, 1998). Nowadays, in industrial countries ethics is considered as an impactful factor in terms of development of every country (Muhammad-Kahn and Mohammadi, 2014).

Ethics is a society's normative rule which is reflected in the behavior of its members. In fact, moral issues are considered as a major problem for organizations, because it manifests a paradox between economic performance (which is measured by incomes, expenses and revenues) and social performance (which is communicated to other parties inside and outside of the organization as commitments) (Adel, 2009). Furthermore, as organizations' environments are increasingly becoming more complex and the rates of occurrence of immoral behaviors are also increasing at the same time; managers' and scholars' attentions have been attracted to the issue of work ethics and ethics management (Faghihi, 2013). On another hand, it is extremely crucial for organizations to consider for ethical standards in today's economy and organizations' ethical behavior plays a crucial role in formation and maintenance of long-term relations between and among an organization and its costumers (Roman, 2005). On this basis, it is clear that a society's perfection is not feasible without human organizations. The existential philosophy behind most organizations implies having the ability for realization of humans' various needs and on the other hand, organizations themselves require expert and efficient human forces in

order to realize their pre-determined goals. Therefore, as we move on; on the one hand the number and variability of organizations increase and on the other hand, behaviors, personal characteristics and human motivations become more complex and more difficult to comprehend. Therefore, recognition of features and characteristics of humans, the manners of formation of behaviors and behavioral causes and the manner of motivation of humans have become the new debates in management psychology (S. Bahar et al. (2005).

In this regard, the increasing trend of application of personality characteristics is highly important (Fred and Ryan, 2005). Most times, personality is considered as the force organizing human's behavior and therefore, it has been in a prominent place in psychology. The fact is that all the things we have achieved so far, or we expect to achieve in future, or even our general health status can be influenced by our own personality as well as the personality of whom we interact with (Schultz, 1997). Therefore, not unlike other professional practitioners, coaches are tasked with special responsibilities and are supposed to take ethical principles and personality characteristics into their accounts.

In addition, researches have also shown that organizations which make progress towards considering for ethical principles and personality characteristics will have a future competitive advantage for themselves which is guaranteed by their current customer satisfaction (Godsends, 2001). In this regard, the recent transformations that have taken place in the concept of marketing, have guided every organization and business towards customer orientation. The ultimate recommendation in every new marketing approach in competitive markets implies maintenance of customers (Amir Shahi, 2010). With respect to importance of customer satisfaction the viewpoint of customer orientation and obtaining customer satisfaction, is considered as a main principle of business and neglecting these principles may lead to a possible elimination from the market. Therefore, if the product does fulfill the customer's expectations, the customer will feel a sense of satisfaction and ultimately, he or she will help the producer organization's sustainability by repeating his or her purchase or encouraging others to use the same product or service (Dadkhah, 2010). Sports organizations are not excluded from this principle and they should take steps for maintaining their customers as well. It seems that work ethics and personality characteristics are a beneficial strategy for satisfaction and maintenance of customers of sports organizations (Afchange et al. 2014). When a customer observes consideration for ethical principles in an organization's behavior, he or she will then reach the belief that the organization's practices are trustworthy and also it doesn't display abusive behaviors. Therefore, the customer will have more tendencies for prolonging his or her relations with that organization (Hansen, 2010). In fact, customers will trust organizations only when they have observed that the organization's practices are fused with ethical principles. Therefore, work ethics, personality characteristics and

customer satisfaction and tendency for repeating the purchase have gained the attention of researchers and marketers (Roman, 2003). In spite of this, when customers' satisfaction is the primary condition for organizations' sustainability, it seems desirable to build organizations based on their customers and general customer orientation. Customers with more satisfaction are more likely to repeat their purchase (Asemani, 2013). Therefore, a sport club's manager should attract more customers and more importantly, he or she should try to keep more customers and lose less; because the cost of attracting a new customer is way more than maintaining one. Comprehending and understanding the needs of customers of sports organizations (Clubs ...) and having commitment for tasks provides us with the possibility for being excellent and gaining supremacy (Saeidi et al. 2015). Since football (soccer) has gained a special popularity as the most popular sport throughout the world and in Iran. Children, youths and even adults have a tendency for football and it seems necessary to study the psychological and environmental factors that affect the behavior of athletes in this field. Realizing the relation between personality characteristics and ethics, not only can help coaches with selecting players and granting others with various privileges and responsibilities, but also it can help consider for the ethical aspect of sports in every society including our Islamic society of Iran. On this basis, several researches have been carried out in the literature of this field, some of which will be explained. (Shirvani and Mehdi poor, 2011).

Finally, with respect to previous researches, we come to know that customers' presence is the primary source of income for sports clubs and also customers' needs must be investigated. Therefore, with respect to importance of considering for ethical principles by sports clubs and organizations, the main purpose of this research is to discuss the relation between sports clubs' customers' satisfaction and coaches' work ethics and personality in Kurdistan Province.

2. Material and Methods

In terms of manner of data collection, the present research is considered as a descriptive-correlative study and also in terms of purpose, it is considered as an applied research which is carried out under field methods. The population of this research includes the staff and customers of governmental and private pools of the province of Kurdistan. The number of the staff is equal to 135 individuals and according to the Morgan's chart, the sample number was determined as 100 individuals. Since this research includes two separate populations, and only the number of the staff of pools is known; the method of synchronization is employed and the same amount of samples is considered for customers as well. For the purpose of data collection, Gregory C. Petty's (1990) questionnaire of

ethics including 23 questions and the factors of interest in work, perseverance, human relations at work environment and collaboration in work was used. The validity of this questionnaire is approved by 15 sports management professors and also its reliability was calculated as 0.81 by the Cronbach's Alpha method. For evaluation of customer satisfaction, the Huang's questionnaire including 19 questions and the components of visuals and looks of the club, personnel, facilities and current equipment. Its validity and reliability are respectively calculated as 0.78 and 0.86. In addition, the short form of questionnaire of personality characteristics was used: aimed at evaluation of players' personality characteristics, the short for of the NEO questionnaire including 60 questions was used. This questionnaire was developed by Caste and McCree in 1982. The first translation of this questionnaire into Persian language was prepared by Kiamehr (2005). This test evaluates 5 major personality characteristics which include Neuroticism (N), extraversion (E), openness of mind towards experiences (O), Agreeableness (A), and conscientiousness (C). The Cronbach's Alpha method has calculated reliability of different aspects of this questionnaire in the range of 0.63 to 0.84.

For the purpose of data analyses, different indexes of descriptive statistics such as average, moderate, standard deviation, abundance and tables are used. In addition, simple regression test, Pearson's correlation test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test were used for investigation of research hypotheses. It is noteworthy to mention that the entire statistical operations were performed with SPSS v21.0 software.

Table1: Results of Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test for normality of data distribution

Test index	Group	Statistic	Number	Sig
K-S	Satisfaction	0.937	100	0.483
	Work ethics	0.900	100	0.403
	Personality characteristics	0.972	100	0.485

Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnoff test manifested in table1, indicate that the independent variable of satisfaction and dependent variables of work ethics and personality characteristics have a normal distribution ($p>0.05$). Therefore, the collected data are homogenous and the curve of this group is considered normal.

Table 2: Correlation matrix of studied variables (satisfaction and work ethics)

Satisfaction	---	Work ethics	Interest in work	Perseverance	Human relations at work environment	Collaboration in work
Sig	R	0.001	0.140	0.019	0.366	0.520
	Sig	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001

** Correlation is significant at 0.01.

Regarding the relation between subscales of satisfaction and work ethics, our findings show that there exists a significant and meaningful relation between satisfaction and work ethics. In addition, the entire components of work ethics are significantly and positively related to customers' satisfaction.

Table 3: Correlation matrix of studied variables (satisfaction, personality characteristics)

Satisfaction	---	Personality characteristics	Neuroticism	Extroversion	Openness of mind...	Agreeability	Consciousness
Sig	R	0.346	0.319	0.088	0.340	0.358	0.351
	Sig	0.001	0.005	0.001	0.003	0.003	0.001

Regarding the relation between sub-scales of satisfaction and NEO personality characteristics, our findings manifest that there exists a significant and meaningful relation between satisfaction and NEO personality characteristics. In addition, the entire components of personality characteristics are significantly and positively related to customers' satisfaction.

Table 4: Results of multivariate regression test for anticipation of customer satisfaction by work ethics

Anticipator variable	Independent variable	F	Sig	R	R2	B	Beta	Sig
Interest in work	Customer satisfaction	10.54	0.001	0.350	0.140	0.370	0.120	0.000
perseverance						0.120	0.400	0.001
Human relation in work environment						0.200	0.180	0.020
Collaboration in work						0.200	0.180	0.001

With respect to the results of table 4, the correlation coefficient is equal to 0.350. This means that the component of work ethics has a total correlation of 0.350 with customer satisfaction. In addition, the determination coefficient is yielded as 0.140 and it signifies that 0.140 units of the variance of customer satisfaction are anticipated by the anticipator variable (components of work ethics). In addition, it can be seen that the entire components of work ethics have a significant anticipation power.

Table 5: Results of multivariate regression test for anticipation personality characteristics

Anticipator variable	Independent variable	F	Sig	R	R2	B	Beta	Sig
Personality characteristics	Customer satisfaction	1.053	0.401	0.239	0.057	0.747	0.197	0.001
neuroticism						0.176	0.042	0.001
extroversion						0.452	0.108	0.001
Openness of mind...						0.825	0.190	0.025
Agreeability						0.356	0.107	0.001
Consciousness						0.451	0.110	0.001

With respect to the results of table 5, the correlation coefficient is equal to 0.239. This means that the component of personality characteristics has a total correlation of 0.239 with customer satisfaction. In addition, the determination coefficient is yielded as 0.057 and it signifies that 0.057 units of the variance of customer satisfaction is anticipated by the anticipator variable (personality characteristics). In addition, it can be seen that the entire components of personality characteristics have a significant anticipation power.

3. Discussion and Conclusions

The purpose of the present research is to discuss the relation between satisfaction of customers and coaches' work ethics and personality in pools of Kurdistan province. Research findings have shown that there exists a significant relation between work ethics and coaches' personality characteristics. This means that as the level of work ethics is improved, coaches' personality characteristics lead to customer satisfaction in pools.

This research has shown that there exists a significant and meaningful relation between fourfold components of ethics including interest in work, perseverance, human relations at work environment and collaborations in work and customer satisfaction. Furthermore, this research has shown that there exists a significant and meaningful relation between sextet components coaches' personality characteristics (neuroticism, extroversion, openness of mind towards experiences, agreeability and consciousness) and customer satisfaction. It means that as each of these components increases, the level of satisfaction also improves among customers. It can be said that one of the most important factors that attracts customers towards pools and impacts their satisfaction is the personality characteristics of coaches. Since the main goal of these sports clubs (pools) is to attract the maximum number of customers, satisfaction could be improved through improvement of work ethics. This includes providing customers with desirable responsiveness, being disciplined, providing suitable and desirable services, understanding customers' needs and efforts for realization of customers' requirements. Also, while studying different items of components of customer, we came to know that being trustworthy and responsiveness have the highest effects on satisfaction. Therefore, the services which are provided for customers in sports clubs should be close to customers' expectations and in addition, Kurdistan province's sports organizations' managers should endeavor for promotion of work ethics and personality characteristics as well as zeroing the gap between customers' expectations and perceptions; because as the provided work ethics and personality characteristics are closer to customers' needs and expectations, customers' satisfaction levels are also improved. Previous researches point out that bold services should be determined by customers' expectations and needs and

even if the provided services are interesting in the view of the provider, but are unable to satisfy the customer's needs, these services cannot and will not be considered as bold services. Therefore, the main goal of coaches and managers of pools in Kurdistan province must be to satisfy customers and establish better relations with customers. There is a direct relation between work ethics and personality characteristics and customer satisfaction and gaining more revenues. In addition, providing customers with suitable and desirable work ethics and personality characteristics requires a system which is highly influential on customers.

On this basis, the findings of this research are consistent with the results obtained by Corona, Alvaro Nueva, Liu, Pollock, Jung, Huck Li and Ramezani, Ghahfarokhi, Syed Javadein, Rostami, and Hamza S. et al. Among other results of this research, it can be pointed to approval of a significant relation that exists between work ethics and customer satisfaction. With respect to table 4, the load factor of work ethics is equal to 0.0937 and the same variable for personality characteristics and satisfaction is respectively equal to 0.0936 and 0.900. These values indicate that this relation is highly powerful and desirable. When a sports club is able to provide its customers with a desirable ethics and also its staff's behavior is desirable, then customers are also willing to pay higher prices in order to be a member of that club. In this regard, on the one hand, the satisfaction situation is satisfied and on the other hand, more revenues are gained. These results are consistent with the results obtained by Corona et al. (2000), Liu (2008), Hamzehpoor Kheradmardi (2013), S. Javadein et al. (2011), Ramezani (2005) and Saeidi et al. (2015). In addition, Ramezani has stated in his research work that being responsiveness is a crucial element in satisfaction of customers and for confirming this result, he has pointed out that there exists a significant relation between customers' economic and social bases and their satisfaction.

With respect to the results of table 4, it is clear that the correlation coefficient is equal to 0.350. This means that that there exists a total correlation of 0.350 between the entire components of work ethics and satisfaction. At the end, it could be stated that the entire components of work ethics have a suitable anticipation power. In addition, as the provided work ethics gets improved, it only results in customer satisfaction when it exceeds the customer's expectations. Therefore, recognition of customers' perceptions and providing services at levels higher than these perceptions can lead to improvement of customer satisfaction and this signifies the high importance of work ethics in pools. These results are consistent with the results obtained by Jalali. F. et al. (2014), Saatchain et al. (2012), S. Javadian et al. (2009), Hawk et al. (2010) and Li et al. (2011).

With respect to the results of table 5, it is clear that the correlation coefficient is equal to 0.239. This means that that there exists a total correlation of 0.239 between the entire components of personality characteristics and satisfaction. At the end, it could be

stated that the entire components of characteristics have a significant anticipation power. In addition, as the provided personality characteristics get improved, it only results in customer satisfaction when it exceeds the customer's expectations. Therefore, recognition of customers' perceptions and providing services at levels higher than these perceptions can lead to improvement of customer satisfaction and this signifies the high importance of personality characteristics in pools. These results are consistent with the results obtained by S. Bahar et al (2005) and Khodabakhsi Koolaei (2013).

It can be concluded that with respect to improved awareness among people, nowadays customers have obtained a general comprehension of different levels of satisfaction. Since a satisfied customer is likely to continue his purchases and make oral advertisements in terms of recommendations to others, paying attention to work ethics and personality characteristics of coaches in pools will have an influential role in development of their perception of satisfaction.

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